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Original Research

LEADERSHIP STYLES AS A CORRELATE OF USE OF KOHA INTEGRATED LIBRARY SOFTWARE IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES IN SOUTH-WEST, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Koha is an open-source integrated library software (ILS) used to manage all library functions. However, it is observed that university libraries in the southwest of Nigeria have not fully utilised it for the provision of library services. Therefore, this study examined leadership styles as a correlate of use of Koha ILS in public university libraries in southwest, Nigeria. *The situational theory of leadership and technology acceptance model* provided the framework. A correlational survey design was adopted. Though, the study was limited to twelve public universities in the six states in Southwest, Nigeria where Koha was in use were used. All the 264 library personnel were enumerated. Leadership styles and use of Koha ILS with reliability coefficients ($\alpha = 0.876$) and ($\alpha = 0.787$) was the instrument developed and used for data collection. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation at 0.05 level of significance. Cataloguing, circulation and OPAC are modules in Koha ILS used to search online catalogues and register library patrons among others. *The leadership styles employed among the supervisors in using Koha ILS were transformational democratic and transactional.* There was a significant and positive correlation between the use of Koha ILS and LS, $r(235) = .350$, $p = .000$. The study suggests that leadership styles significantly influence the use of Koha ILS in southwest Nigerian public university libraries. It study recommends that supervisors should consistently emphasize and sustain transformational, democratic, and transactional leadership styles to encourage superior performance, leading to increased production, competitiveness, and effectiveness

Keywords: Integrated Library Software, Koha ILS, Leadership Styles, Open-Source Software, Public University Libraries

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1.0 Introduction

The rapid evolution of technology has raised the bar for library services, driving modern libraries to rely on the Integrated Library System (ILS) for effective management. An Integrated Library System (ILS) is a comprehensive suite of software designed to manage and automate various tasks and processes within a library. It constitutes a pivotal tool in the contemporary library landscape, purpose-built to manage core administrative tasks within libraries. It functions as an integrated software solution encompassing modules for circulation, serials, acquisition, cataloguing, and OPAC, addressing a multitude of library functions. ILS has been essential to the evolution of libraries, ushering them from traditional to automated, automated to electronic, electronic to digital, and ultimately to virtual environments. ILS enhances the efficiency of university libraries by providing access to their resources and holdings.

Several open-source integrated-library software, including Evergreen, Dspace, Eprint, Fedora, OPALS (Open-Source Automated Library System), Greenstone, OpenBiblio, Invenio, PMB (PhpMyBibli), CodeAchi, Polaris, NewGenLib, BiblioteQ, and Koha, have made significant inroads into Nigerian libraries. However, according to Omeluzor et al. (2019), while some open-source library software has flourished with substantial usage, many others have fallen short, resulting in the squandering of time, resources, and effort. Khan (2020), Koha is a noteworthy innovation that

provides a wide range of benefits like affordability, flexible coding and shared accountability for system rules. It offers librarians a great and affordable alternative to commercial software.

However, library personnel anticipate that Koha ILS will help the institution's library function efficiently. The leadership styles exhibited will determine the performance success to be recorded. If the leadership styles are effective, they will promote performance. Effective leadership influences the improvement of people's lives, encourages collaboration, cultivates a passion for technology, and improves an organisation's overall performance. Research has demonstrated that strong leadership can elevate staff enthusiasm, attitudes, and productivity through technological advancement. It is observed that the leadership approach of university management leaders is reflected in their character and has a lasting impact on their interactions with subordinates. Regardless of specific traits and behaviours, library leaders are expected to apply the most appropriate leadership style that will encourage the integration of new technologies.

Uwandu (2021) underscored the significance of leadership styles in achieving service effectiveness and stressed the importance of supervisory officers possessing leadership skills to lead and manage their subordinates effectively. It is suggested that adopting and implementing the right leadership style leads to employee satisfaction, resulting in more

successful employee performance. Different leadership styles have different emotional impacts on the followers they are meant to influence, and the best leadership philosophies are balanced and situation-specific. In this regard, a librarian's leadership style should align with the values, preferences, culture, norms, and guidelines of the organisation.

In the context of Nigerian university libraries, leadership styles vary among their leaders. Ukaidi (2019) highlighted that an organisation's leadership style significantly impacts its operations. An effective leadership style can promote productivity, empower individuals, boost employee morale and motivation, and contribute positively to the organisation. However, further research is required to delve into the specific leadership styles of supervisors. While many studies have explored the use of Koha ILS in Nigerian public university libraries, none have specifically examined leadership styles. Filling this gap is imperative. Therefore, this study aims to investigate leadership styles as a correlate of use of Koha ILS in public university libraries in South-West, Nigeria.

1.1 Statement of Problem

The demands of 21st-century library users differ from what is expected of traditional service delivery methods. Koha ILS has brought about an incredible change in Nigerian university libraries, which is changing historical narratives. Koha is an open-source integrated library software (ILS) used for managing library

collections and automating various library operations. University libraries in Nigeria and other parts of the world are increasingly using Koha ILS. However, despite its substantial advantages, preliminary investigations and observations revealed that university libraries in the southwest of Nigeria have not fully utilised Koha ILS in the provision of library services. It has been discovered that leadership styles may significantly impact the use of Koha ILS in university libraries. This suggests that the ineffective leadership style of supervisors in university libraries may be responsible for the decline in the utilisation of Koha ILS in public university libraries. This study is therefore set out to investigate leadership styles as a correlate of the use of Koha ILS in public university libraries in South-West, Nigeria.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to examine leadership styles as a correlate of use of Koha ILS in public university libraries in South-West, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to, identify the modules in Koha ILS used, ascertain the frequency of use of Koha, find out the purpose of use of Koha ILS, identify the prominent leadership style employed for using Koha ILS and investigate the relationship between leadership styles and the use of Koha ILS in public university libraries in South-West, Nigeria.

1.3 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the

study:

1. What are the modules in Koha ILS used for library operations in public university libraries in south-west Nigeria?
2. How often is the use of modules in Koha ILS for library tasks in public university libraries in Southwest Nigeria?
3. What are the purposes of using Koha ILS in public university libraries in south-west Nigeria?
4. What prominent leadership style is employed for using Koha ILS in public university libraries in South-West, Nigeria?

1.4 Hypothesis

The null hypothesis was formulated for the study and tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between leadership style and the use of Koha ILS in public university libraries in South-West, Nigeria.

2.0 Literature review

2.1 Use of Koha ILS in Public University Libraries

Koha is an ILS that is widely used in libraries to manage their collections and provide essential library services Tella and Olajide (2020) investigated the influence of Koha ILS on library services and the findings indicated that Koha had a favourable influence on the libraries studied. Ojedokun et al. (2021) found that Koha ILS improved the technological procedures and services provided by Bowen University Library.

Otunla et al. (2022) surveyed to assess the utilization of Koha ILS across Nigeria's six geopolitical zones. The findings revealed that cataloguing, OPAC, and circulation modules were used daily but the serials and acquisition modules were never used. Igbudu et al. (2020) investigated the influence of Koha on technical operations. Their findings indicated that the cataloguing module was used for library technical operations. Uzomba et al. (2021) findings when investigating the usage of Koha ILS in Nigerian universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education libraries revealed that the OPAC, cataloguing, and circulation modules were used daily for user registration, book cataloguing, charging and discharging of books and accessing the OPAC.

Chukwueke (2022) investigated the utilization of Koha ILS and the findings indicated that the OPAC, circulation, and cataloguing modules were used daily for record addition, search queries, metadata creation, user registration, and item tracking. Omopupa, Adedeji, and Sulyman-Haroon (2020) investigated the extent of the use of Koha ILS. Their findings revealed that the cataloguing and circulation modules were highly utilised, suggesting that these modules were essential to daily library operations. Jamogha et al. (2022) investigated the operational Koha modules and their purposes. The study found that acquisition, cataloguing, circulation, and serials modules were functioning and used for making payments and placing orders for book and serials purchases. Omopupa, Adedeji, Kehinde,

Abdulsalam, and Abubakar (2020) conducted a comparative research study on the level of Koha usage. Their findings revealed that all Koha modules were utilised at Bowen University Library, while the University of Ilorin Library predominantly used cataloguing and circulation modules. Alikobaet al. (2019) examined the modules in Koha used. Their findings indicated that cataloguing, serials, OPAC, and circulation modules were utilized, while the acquisition module was not working in the libraries. Abdulrahman et al. (2020) investigated the level of Koha use and their findings indicated that the cataloguing module was used daily for library operations.

2.2 Leadership Styles in Public University Libraries

Leadership styles in university libraries can vary depending on the library's culture, the leadership styles of the heads of the library, and the preferences and characteristics of individual leaders. The findings of Okere and Olorunfemi (2020) when investigating the leadership styles in academic libraries revealed that library managers in the region predominantly exhibited a mixture of transformational and transactional leadership styles. Chukwusa (2019) examined the perceived leadership styles of university librarians in the southeast of Nigeria and discovered that federal university librarians in the area predominantly employed a democratic leadership style. Mayowa-Adebara and Opeke (2019) investigated the impact of leadership styles on employee commitment in university

libraries. Their findings revealed that the transformational leadership style was employed by supervisors and influenced the staff.

Orewa's (2019) findings revealed that autocratic, democratic, and laissez-faire leadership styles were used by library leaders but democratic leadership was the most commonly used. The findings revealed further that, the democratic leadership style enhanced job performance. Akanmidu et al. (2021) findings identified transactional and transformational as types of leadership styles utilised in the library. The findings also revealed further that transactional and transformational leadership styles influence the service delivery of librarians. Urhefe-Okotie's (2022) findings showed that the transformational leadership style influenced the transactional style on job performance. Akidi and Chukwueke's (2020) results indicated that the acceptance of transformational, democratic, and autocratic leadership styles by university librarians resulted in improved staff productivity and more effective contributions to libraries. They found that democratic and transformational styles were predominantly adopted, while autocratic styles had limited usage. Okpokwasili and Kalu's (2020) results indicated that the autocratic leadership style did not improve the performance of members of staff. Olise et al. (2020) findings revealed that the democratic leadership style was dominant among librarians in the libraries. The results also showed that leadership style influences the use of technology.

Research has shown that leadership styles significantly influence the performance and job satisfaction of library professionals in various settings. For instance, studies have indicated that democratic leadership styles tend to positively affect administrative effectiveness and job satisfaction in library environments (Offem, 2021). Additionally, leadership styles can differ in their impact, with transformational leadership often seen as promoting positive outcomes (Uwandu, 2021). Barrido and Abadiano's (2020) findings revealed that democratic, transformational and transactional leadership styles were put to use by library heads.

2.3 Leadership Styles and Use of Koha ILS in Public University Libraries

The role of different technologies within organisations varies based on the prevailing leadership styles (Andriopulos & Lowe, 2019). Effective leadership style motivates staff to adopt new software, manages expectations, addresses setbacks, and ensures continued technology use within the organization (Aziz et al., 2020). Studies on leadership styles in university libraries have unveiled a range of styles employed by library leaders. For example, Kumar and Kapoor's (2021) findings suggested that technology tended to positively impact the effectiveness of various leadership styles in fostering teamwork within the organization. Likewise, Kaya and Gurhan's (2021) findings revealed that technology had a

favourable effect on leadership styles.

The findings conducted by Racero et al. (2022) showed that the usage of OSS in teaching was influenced by both transactional and transformational leadership styles. Barrido and Abadiano's (2020) findings showed that transactional leadership style influences the utilization of ICT application tools. Purwanto et al. (2019) results revealed that transactional and transformational leadership styles significantly influence the use of the software. Kangeri's (2021) findings unveiled that transformational and transactional leadership styles influence the utilization of technology.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

This study used the Situational Leadership Theory (SLT), developed by Paul and Ken in 1969, and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) developed by Davis in 1989. SLT suggests that effective leadership depends on the situation, followers' maturity, and the appropriate style and tactics. TAM investigates perceived usefulness and ease of use, which are critical factors influencing users' usage behaviour. SLT is relevant in this study as it improves Koha ILS adoption rates when supervisors make use of the appropriate leadership style, increases efficiency when support and guidance are provided by supervisors, and enhances user experience when library personnel are involved in the decision-making process. TAM posits that if users perceive Koha as useful, they are more likely to adopt and use it

3.0 Methods

3.1 Research design

This study employed a survey research design of a correlational type. In correlation research, data are collected to determine whether or not and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more variables. The design is appropriate according to Peretomode, Peretomode and Ibe (2020), it is used to study statistical relationships between the two variables.

3.2 Population

The population of this study comprised two hundred and sixty-four (264) library personnel (professional librarians and para-professionals) in twelve (12) public university libraries where the Koha ILS is used in South-West, Nigeria.

3.3 Sample and Sampling Technique

This study adopted the total enumeration of two hundred and sixty-four (264) professional librarians and para-professionals in twelve public university libraries in Southwest, Nigeria.

3.4 Instrument of the Study

The instrument tagged *Leadership Style and Use of Koha ILS Questionnaire (LSUKQ)* was used for collecting data for this study. The questionnaire was constructed by the researcher based on a literature review.

3.5 Validity and Reliability of Instrument

The questionnaire was validated by experts to ensure its content and face was valid. It was

thereafter administered to the 30 University of Ilorin library personnel, University of Ilorin, Kwara State in the North Central, Nigeria which is not included in the population of this study. The instrument had the following reliability coefficient: the use of Koha ILS ($\alpha = 0.787$) and the leadership styles employed in using the Koha ILS ($\alpha = 0.876$).

3.6 Method Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics (frequency counts, percentages, the mean and standard deviation) were used to answer the research questions while Pearson Correlation was used to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance.

3.7 Questionnaire Administration and Response Rate

Two hundred and sixty-four (264) copies of the questionnaire were administered to the library personnel working in 12 public university libraries in southwest, Nigeria, two hundred and forty-four (244) copies were returned, out of these, two hundred and thirty-seven (237) were valid and useful for the computation of the analysis of the study yielding 92.42% response rate.

3.8 Ethical Considerations for the Study

The researcher acknowledged all the scholars whose research works were cited in this study. The participants' consent was sought. Participants were informed of the purpose of the study. Research participation was entirely

voluntary. The participants' identities were kept private. The information gathered from the participants was used strictly for this study.

4.0 Results

Table 1: Demographic Information of Respondents in Public University Libraries in South-West, Nigeria

Name of Institutions	Frequency	(%)
Federal University of Oye, Ekiti State	10	4.2
Federal University of Akure, Ondo State	25	10.5
Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile -Ife	35	14.8
Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun State	28	11.8
Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State	5	2.1
Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomosho, Oyo State	10	4.2
Lagos State University of Science and Technology, Ikorodu, Lagos State	20	8.4
Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos State	28	11.8
Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology, Okitipupa, Ondo State	9	3.8
Ekiti State University, Ado -Ekiti	35	14.8
Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology, Ikere -Ekiti, Ekiti State	17	7.2
Osun State University, Osogbo, Osun State	15	6.3
Total	237	100
Gender of Respondents		
Male	129	54.4
Female	108	45.6
Total	237	100
Qualification of Respondents		
DLS/ND in LIS	51	21.5
HND in LIS	33	13.9
BLIS	40	16.9
PGD in LIS	11	4.6
MLIS	73	30.8
PhD in LIS	29	12.2
Total	237	100

Status of Respondents

Assistant Library Officer	13	5.5
Library Officer	27	11.4
Higher Library Officer	21	8.9
Senior Library Officer	27	11.4
Principal Library Officer	20	8.4
Chief Library Officer	11	4.6
Assistant Librarian	13	5.5
Librarian II	24	10.1
Librarian I	18	7.6
Senior Librarian	31	13.1
Principal Librarian	24	10.1
Deputy University Librarian	6	2.5
University Librarian	2	0.8
Total	237	100

Source: Author's computation (2023)

Table 1 shows the personal data of respondents in public university libraries in Southwest, Nigeria. The table indicates that Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti and Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife had the majority of respondents, 35(14.8%) respectively. Of the male respondents, 129(54.47%) participated more than the female respondents. The majority

of the respondents, 73(30.8%), possessed MLIS. The majority of the respondents were senior Librarians, 31(13.1%).

Research Question 1: What are the modules in Koha ILS used for library operations in public university libraries in South-West, Nigeria?

Table 2: Modules in Koha ILS used for library operations

Items	Yes	
	Frequency	%
Acquisitions	110	46.4
Serials	116	48.9
OPAC	161	67.9
Circulation	175	73.8
Cataloguing	181	76.4

Source: Author's computation (2023)

Table 2 shows the modules in Koha ILS used for library operations in public university libraries in southwest, Nigeria. The modules in Koha ILS used among the respondents are on a YES or NO response. Results revealed that cataloguing module 181(76.4%), circulation module 175(73.8%) and OPAC module 161 (67.9%)

were used for library operations. Hence, catalogue, circulation and OPAC modules were put to use when performing library operations in public university libraries in southwest, Nigeria. Research Question 2: How often is the use of modules in Koha ILS for library tasks in public university libraries in Southwest Nigeria?

Table 3: Frequency of use of modules in Koha in the public university libraries

Modules in Koha	Daily	Weekly	Once in a while	Never	x	SD
Circulation Module	120 50.6%	50 21.1%	31 13.1%	36 15.2%	3.07	1.12
Serials Module	61 25.7%	54 22.8%	43 18.1%	79 33.3%	2.41	1.20
Acquisition Module	77 32.5%	38 16.0%	38 16.0%	84 35.4%	2.46	1.27
OPAC Module	106 44.7%	61 25.7%	38 16.0%	32 13.5%	3.02	1.07
Cataloguing Module	144 60.8%	43 18.1%	27 11.4%	23 9.7%	3.30	1.01
Grand mean = 2.85						

Source: Author's computation (2023)

Decision rule: Mean (\bar{x}) 1.00 -1.74 = Never; 1.75 - 2.49 = Once in a while; 2.50-3.24 = Weekly and 3.25-4.00 = Daily

Table 3 shows the frequency of use of modules in Koha ILS for library tasks in public university libraries in southwest, Nigeria. The cataloguing module (3.30) was used daily. The circulation module (3.07), and OPAC module (3.02) were

used weekly while the acquisition module (2.46) and serial module (2.41) were used once in a while. Hence, cataloguing, circulation, and OPAC were modules mostly used for library tasks.

Research Question 3: What are the purposes of the use of Koha ILS in public university libraries in South-West, Nigeria?

Table 4: Purpose of using Koha ILS in the public university library

Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean \bar{x}	Std. Dev.
It is used in patron registration.	113 47.7%	110 46.4%	11 4.6%	3 1.3%	3.40	.64
It is used to add and edit bibliographic records of books.	102 43.0%	122 51.5%	10 4.2%	3 1.3%	3.36	.62
It is used for managing library stock.	94 39.7%	126 53.2%	17 7.2%	0 0.0%	3.32	.60
It is used in accessing web OPAC.	109 46.0%	106 44.7%	19 8.0%	3 1.3%	3.35	.68
It is used to search the online catalogue	117 49.4%	106 44.7%	13 5.5%	1 0.4%	3.43	.61
It is used in charging and discharging books.	110 46.4%	103 43.5%	19 8.0%	5 2.1%	3.34	.71
It serves to track the ordering, payment, and delivery of books.	79 33.3%	112 47.3%	31 13.1%	15 6.3%	3.07	.84
It is used to keep track of periodicals.	74 31.2%	131 55.3%	24 10.1%	8 3.4%	3.14	.72
It is used in generating reports	86 36.3%	116 48.9%	24 10.1%	11 4.6%	3.16	.79
Grand mean = 3.29						

Source: Author's computation (2023)

Decision rule: Mean (\bar{x}) ≥ 3.29 is accepted

Table 4 shows the mean (\bar{x}) responses of respondents on the purpose of using Koha ILS in public university libraries in South-West, Nigeria with corresponding standard deviation values. Data presented in Table 3 reveals that the items with the mean (\bar{x}) equal or greater than 3.29 are accepted as the purpose of using Koha ILS. Koha is used to search the online catalogue (3.43), register patrons (3.40), add and edit bibliographic records of books (3.36), access web OPAC (3.35), charge and discharge books (3.34), and manage library stock (3.32). Hence,

Koha is used to search online catalogues, *patron registration, add and edit books' bibliographic records, access web OPAC, charge and discharge books, and manage the library stock* in public university libraries in southwest, Nigeria.

Research Question 4: What prominent leadership style is employed for using Koha ILS in public university libraries in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 5: Leadership style employed in using Koha ILS

Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean x	Std. Dev.
My supervisor believes I must be closely supervised if I am to use Koha ILS for library service delivery.	58 24.5%	75 31.6%	86 36.3%	18 7.6%	2.73	.91
My supervisor insists that I am indeed sluggish in using Koha ILS.	22 9.3%	62 26.2%	111 46.8%	42 17.7%	2.27	.86
My supervisor believes that I need to be disciplined for failure to understand how to use Koha ILS for library service delivery.	23 9.7%	69 29.1%	108 45.6%	37 15.6%	2.32	.85
My supervisor communicates very little with me on how to use Koha ILS.	37 15.6%	76 32.1%	105 44.3%	19 8.0%	2.55	.85
I lack direction and feel uneasy about my job while using Koha ILS.	18 7.6%	58 24.5%	117 49.4%	44 18.6%	2.21	.83
Average mean of Autocratic leadership style					2.41	.62
My supervisor gives orders and clarifies the procedure on how to use Koha ILS.	55 23.2%	112 47.3%	61 25.7%	9 3.8%	2.89	.79
My supervisor inspires me to use Koha ILS.	69 29.1%	125 52.7%	35 14.8%	8 3.4%	3.07	.75
I easily exchange ideas with my supervisor without fear of sanction anytime I have difficulty using Koha ILS.	77 32.5%	124 52.3%	29 12.2%	7 3.0%	3.14	.74
My supervisor assists me in discovering my passion for using Koha ILS.	66 27.8%	121 51.1%	46 19.4%	4 1.7%	3.05	.73
My supervisor believes that I am capable and will use Koha ILS to carry out library tasks.	84 35.4%	120 50.6%	25 10.5%	8 3.4%	3.18	.75
Average mean of Democratic leadership style					3.07	.55
My supervisor allows me to resolve any Koha ILS complex issues on my own.	51 21.5%	120 50.6%	57 24.1%	9 3.8%	2.89	.77
My supervisor allows me to use Koha ILS the way I want it.	55 23.2%	120 50.6%	55 23.2%	7 3.0%	2.94	.76
My supervisor does not supervise me strictly when I am using Koha ILS.	34 14.3%	128 54.0%	65 27.4%	10 4.2%	2.78	.73
My supervisor avoids interference with me on using Koha ILS.	29 12.2%	111 46.8%	87 36.7%	10 4.2%	2.67	.74
My supervisor gives me a lot of independence while performing my duties using Koha ILS.	63 26.6%	128 54.0%	37 15.6%	9 3.8%	3.03	.75

Average mean of Laissez-faire leadership style					2.86	.54
My supervisor tells me what to do if I want to be rewarded for using Koha ILS.	55 23.2%	119 50.2%	53 22.4%	10 4.2%	2.92	.78
My supervisor tells me the standard I have to know on using Koha ILS to carry out my work.	73 30.8%	130 54.9%	32 13.5%	2 0.8%	3.15	.67
My supervisor provides rewards when I reach my goals using Koha ILS.	56 23.6%	116 48.9%	57 24.1%	8 3.4%	2.92	.78
My supervisor calls my attention to what I can get for what I accomplish using Koha ILS.	48 20.3%	145 61.2%	35 14.8%	9 3.8%	2.97	.71
My supervisor takes correct action when Koha ILS problems arise.	58 24.5%	144 60.8%	29 12.2%	6 2.5%	3.07	.68
Average mean of Transactional leadership style					3.01	.51
My supervisor makes me feel good around him/her when using Koha ILS.	62 26.2%	149 62.9%	22 9.3%	4 1.7%	3.13	.63
My supervisor helps me to rethink ideas that I had never questioned before on how to use Koha ILS.	56 23.6%	137 57.8%	40 16.9%	4 1.7%	3.03	.68
My supervisor helps me to develop myself on how to use Koha ILS	75 31.6%	141 59.5%	19 8.0%	2 0.8%	3.21	.62
My supervisor is a person I am proud to be associated with when using Koha ILS.	77 32.5%	131 55.3%	28 11.8%	1 0.4%	3.19	.65
My supervisor gives personal attention to me when I seem rejected of using Koha ILS.	64 27.0%	132 55.7%	31 13.1%	10 4.2%	3.05	.75
Average mean of Transformational leadership style					3.12	.48
Grand mean = 2.89						

Source: Author's computation (2023)

Decision rule: Mean (x_{\square}) ≥ 2.89 is accepted

Table 5 shows the prominent leadership styles employed by supervisors for utilising Koha in South-west public university libraries in Nigeria. The decision rule categorized the leadership styles into two levels; accept and reject, based on the grand mean of 2.89. The leadership styles namely autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire, transformational and transactional were measured. The average mean

(x_{\square}) for each type of leadership style was also calculated. The mean (x_{\square}) greater than or equal to 2.89 is accepted while less than or equal to 2.88 is rejected as the prominent leadership styles employed for using Koha ILS. The results revealed that transformational ($x_{\square} = 3.12$), democratic ($x_{\square} = 3.07$) and transactional ($x_{\square} = 3.01$) were accepted as prominent leadership styles employed for using Koha ILS. Hence,

transformational, transactional, and democratic leadership styles are *prominent leadership styles employed* for using Koha ILS in public university libraries in South-West, Nigeria.

Testing of Hypothesis

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between leadership styles and the use of Koha ILS in public university libraries in southwest,

Table 6: Leadership styles and use of Koha ILS
Descriptive Statistics

Correlations

Variable	N	x	s	r value	Sig. (2-tailed)
Use of Koha ILS	237	3.02	.41	.350**	.000
Leadership styles	237	2.89	.38		

** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed), df = 235, Critical r-value = 0.148

A Pearson correlation coefficient was computed to ascertain the linear relationship between leadership style and the use of Koha ILS in public university libraries in Southwest Nigeria. The result revealed that the calculated

$$\tau = .350, \quad N = 237; p = .000) \text{ betwe}$$

between leadership style and the use of Koha ILS. This showed that an increase in the leadership style of the respondent leads to an increase in the use of Koha ILS in public university libraries in South-West Nigeria.

4.0 Discussion of Findings

Results on the modules in Koha ILS used for library operations in public university libraries in Southwest, Nigeria indicated that cataloguing, circulation and OPAC were modules used for library operations. Hence, cataloguing, circulation and OPAC were put to use when performing library operations. The results supported the study of many researchers.

The result is sustained by Chukwueke (2022), Otunla et al. (2022) and Alikoba et al. (2019) that cataloguing, OPAC and circulation were modules used for library tasks. The result is corroborated by Igbudu et al. (2020) that the cataloguing module was used for library technical operations. The result agrees with Omopupa et al. (2020) that cataloguing and circulation modules are used for library operations.

Results on the frequency of use of modules of Koha ILS for library tasks in public university libraries in Nigeria southwest indicated that the cataloguing module was used daily while circulation and OPAC modules were used weekly for library tasks. Hence, cataloguing, circulation and OPAC were modules mostly used for library tasks. The result is in line with the findings of Otunla et al. (2022) that OPAC and circulation modules were used daily. The result concurred with the findings of Chukueke

(2022), Uzomba et al. (2021), and Omopupa et al. (2022) that OPAC, cataloguing and circulation modules were used daily for library operations. It agrees with the findings of Abdulrahman et al. (2020) that the cataloguing module was used daily in the National Library of Nigeria, Abuja.

Results on the purpose of using Koha ILS in public university libraries in Nigeria Southwest indicated that Koha ILS was used to search online catalogues, *patron registration, update and modify books' bibliographic records, access web OPAC, charge and discharge books in the library and manage the library stock*. Hence, Koha ILS is used for library tasks. The findings confirmed the study of numerous scholars. The result is supported by the findings of Tella and Olajide (2020) that Koha ILS favourably impacted library services. It agrees with the findings of Ojedokun et al. (2021) that Koha assisted in streamlining the technological operations of the library and facilitating the efficient provision of information services and the library. The results corroborate the outcome of Chukwueke (2022), and Uzomba et al. (2021) that Koha is used to register users, charge and discharge books, classify and catalogue books, browse web-based OPAC systems, perform searches, and manage library stock. The outcome confirmed the findings of Jamogha et al. (2022) that Koha ILS is used for ordering books and making payments which is widely regarded as being useful.

Results on the prominent leadership styles employed in using Koha ILS in public

university libraries in Southwest Nigeria showed that transformational, democratic, and transactional leadership styles are employed by supervisors *in Koha use* in public university libraries in Southwest Nigeria. Hence, the supervisor employed effective leadership styles that would improve employee work performance and productivity. This study affirms the standpoint of Barrido and Abadiano (2018), Akanmidu et al. (2021) and Urhefe-Okotie (2022) that transactional and transformational leadership styles are employed by librarians to promote library service delivery. The results corroborate Chukwusa (2019), Nwaigwe (2019), Olise et al. (2020) and Offem (2021) that democratic leadership is most frequently used by library heads, and it has a favourable impact on librarians' fulfilment in their jobs. The results are consistent with Okere and Olorunfemi (2020), who found that library managers primarily displayed a blend of transformational and transactional leadership styles. The results corroborate those of Mayowa-Adebara and Opeke (2019), who found that the transformational leadership style had a greater impact on staff commitment than the transactional leadership style. The results corroborate those of Akidi and Chukwueke (2020), who found that university librarians' adoption of transformational and democratic leadership styles increased staff productivity and improved their ability to contribute to the libraries.

Additionally, this study demonstrated that the use of Koha ILS and leadership style had a

strong and favourable link. As a result, the null hypothesis which held that there is no meaningful correlation between leadership styles and the use of Koha was rejected. The results demonstrated that effective leadership shapes employees' adoption of newly implemented technologies within the organisation and is essential for controlling expectations and maintaining the use of technology. The results supported the claims made by Kumar and Kapoor (2021) that technology use has a positive impact on the way various leadership styles promote teamwork within an enterprise. This research supports the findings of Barrido and Abadiano (2018), Olise et al. (2020), Kaya and Gurhan (2021) and Kangeri (2021) who found that a transactional leadership style has a major impact on how ICT application tools are used. The results supported the claims made by Purwanto et al. (2019) and Aziz et al. (2020) that leadership styles have a positive and significant influence on the use of food safety management software. The results supported the claims made by Purwanto et al. (2019) and Racero et al. (2022) that both transactional and transformational leadership influenced the use of OSS in the classroom.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

This research provides significant insights to better understand key determinants of the use of Koha ILS in public university libraries. Based on the findings of the study, this study concludes that the use of Koha ILS in public university libraries in southwest, Nigeria is determined by

leadership styles. Cataloguing, OPAC and circulation modules' used by library personnel for library tasks are crucial to attaining library objectives. However, this could be possible when the supervisors make use of appropriate leadership styles. Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that greater use of transformational, democratic, and transactional leadership styles should be continually emphasized and sustained by supervisors. This will enable them to get the best from their subordinates leading to high production, competitiveness and effectiveness. Library management in southwest Nigeria should conduct in-house training and retraining for staff on Koha's modules, specifically acquisition and serial modules, to improve library operations efficiency.

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